

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

Report on Workshop 2

Intensive case study: Opening nature and the outdoors to Black, Asian and Ethnic Minority communities.¹

Sunday 7th April at Mercure Lambert Hotel in Oxfordshire UK

From CU: Geraldine Brown (GB), Alex Franklin (AF), Barbara Smith (BS) and Lindy Binder (LB)

From Dadima's CIC: Geeta Ludhra (GL), Subash Ludhra (SL), plus 8 participants who have attended Dadima's walks.

Independent filmmaker: Ben Cook (BC)

Time	Item	Lead(s)
9.30-9.45am arrival	Welcome refreshments from 9.30am onwards.	GL & SL
10.00-10.15	Morning session welcome, overview of the day & introductions. New participants welcome.	SL & GL
10.15	Learning Community check-in: Revisiting information on postcards and meditative introduction with essential oils led by a Learning Community participant.	LB, LC participant
10.30	Deep diving into biodiversity	BS
11.30	Comfort break	
11.45	Learning from the system mapping exercise in workshop 1 and Leverage Points exercise	AF
12.30	Lunch	GL & SL
13.15	Participatory filmmaking and activity	GB, BC, BS
14.15	Comfort Break	
14.30	Summary of journey, next meetings	AF, GB
15.05	Final reflections: Postcard thoughts Keeping ideas warm in-between meetings	GL/SL

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Introductions

GL and SL greeted the attendees and provided an opportunity for each person to introduce themselves and share something about their interest in nature and biodiversity.

The Learning Community comprises eleven participants, from ethnic minority Communities, who have previously participated in walks organised by Dadima's CIC. Geeta and Subash are the walk leaders and occupy a dual role as Planet 4B Learning Community participants and co-facilitators, alongside the CU team.

Eight participants attended Workshop 2, and this was the first session for two of the participants.

See below for demographic information for all those who have attended at least one workshop:

None of the participants identifies as having a disability.

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Non-dependent children: over 16

Dependent children: under 16 or aged 16-18 and in full time education

Other multi-person household: flat shares, single parents with non-dependent children only, households containing more than one couple or single parent.

The two new participants gave **informed consent** to participate in the Learning Community, as well as agreeing to allow PLANET4B to use any images collected as part of the project.

The session started with LB leading an activity to encourage reflection on the postcards of hopes that participants had written at the end of Workshop 1. Hopes identified included planting and growing, going for more walks and further reflection on the concept of biodiversity. She then led a brief exercise to capture participants’ feeling(s) about the second workshop.

A development from Workshop 1 was that a participant of the Learning Community volunteered to contribute to the opening session and lead a **reflective meditation-style activity using essential oils**. She gave out samples of two scents: ginger and vanilla (with their identity not initially revealed), and invited everyone to close their eyes, breathe in, and think about what feeling or memories each scent evoked. The warming and invigorating properties of ginger is known to stimulate mental energy and

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concentration. Its spicy and energising aroma is linked to promoting focus and supporting memory recall. The softer, sweeter vanilla, reminded people of their childhood, baking with parents or grandparents, or ice cream and holidays. This activity was very well received, and the participant shared that she had delivered a similar activity with participants on a Dadima’s walk.

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Deep Dive into Biodiversity

Feedback from Workshop 1 and a re-occurring theme arising in one-to-one interviews, was the interest amongst the Learning Community to engage more with the science of biodiversity. Drawing on the expertise of BS, the second activity was an hour's deep dive into biodiversity.

BS started by inviting the Learning Community to discuss the following questions:

1. What is biodiversity? And
2. What biodiversity do we want?

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The Learning Community reached a consensus about the complexity of biodiversity, acknowledging that it is an interdependent and connected part of our ecosystem, and expressing concern about political and social forces that control its fate. The discussion was rich, and the group agreed that biodiversity is all-encompassing and difficult to define. Some highlights of the conversation are listed below:

All things co-existing ... the birds, the bees, the trees, the plants, humans

Things growing wild – not manicured greenery...

*We are servants of nature, not masters...we're not saying get rid of science... but if we start to look at nature through a **sacred** lens, that respect comes in.*

BS outlined various perspectives and explored distinctions between nature and wildlife, biodiversity, and ecosystems. She introduced the Learning Community to ways biodiversity can be measured at various levels and highlighted legislation that exists to protect it. BS's session was recorded so it could be shared with the three members of the Learning Community who were unable to attend the workshop.

An outcome of the deep dive into biodiversity is the Learning Community have agreed to participate in a citizen science activity. Some suggestions were made and over lunch the group could write down their ideas on sticky-notes, which were later collated as shown.

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- **Kitchen cupboard** might include taking a photo of some staple items from our kitchen cupboard and from these, do one or more of the following: a map of where the food comes from, the energy/transport costs associated with the items, count the number of ingredients – seeking those with fewer, looking at what chemicals the foods contain, and understanding the biodiversity impacts of the food with the intention of affecting food decision making.
- **Bird counting**, potentially using an app (such as Merlin), counting the number and variety of birds that visit a feeder, or identifying the different birds, or butterflies at a particular time on a particular day, noting environmental factors such as weather.
- **Moth trap** – the potential to make our own moth traps to see what moths visit our gardens, and how this varies depending on where we live.
- **Growing something** – either on a windowsill, balcony or garden, allowing it to flower and seeing what other species visit it. Potential plants mentioned: ginger (x2), coriander, a herb, vegetables.

Other suggestions from the ideas board include:

- Petition to dub some of the best nature documentaries into Hindi/Gujrati/Punjabi/Urdu
- Buy seasonal fruit
- Week of eating non processed foods
- Foraging exercise
- Walk a set distance from your house and count number of different animals/birds, flora/fauna spotted
- What is the base knowledge of “family members on key questions about biodiversity?”

Before Workshop 3 and via email and the WhatsApp group, we propose to home in on a citizen science project that will most engage this Learning Community.

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Leverage Points from System mapping

As part of the PLANET4B initiative, the Intensive Case Studies team is tasked with exploring leverage points in collaboration with the Learning Community, and where elements identified during the system mapping exercise from the first workshop might fit.

The purpose of the exercise is to map the key factors that influence the system (Dadima’s) identified in Workshop 1 onto the twelve [Leverage Points](#) (Meadows, 1999).

AF gave a brief introduction to the Leverage Points framework theory and the 12 individual Leverage Points (divided into four subsections: materials, feedback, design and intent). She provided an illustration of how each of individual Leverage Point could be interpreted in the context of exploring opportunities and barriers to opening up the British countryside to ethnic minority communities.

The presentation of the Leverage Points framework generated for some participants a strong critical reaction, with several follow-up questions for further clarification. Following an initial plenary discussion and debate on the value of working with this framework, Learning Community members were asked to continue with testing and critiquing the suitability of the theoretical framework in smaller groups. Within this case-study, participants struggled to connect to the model and see its relevance.

The Learning Community was split into three groups and included a member from the CU team and given four tables to populate. Example below:

Intent	
Envisaged system	
Transformative interventions	
How to prompt/deepen/ enable	

The Learning Community’s engagement in the Leverage Point activity varied. There was a consensus that it was an unhelpful framework, and it was challenging to accurately select which leverage point or subgroup some of the interventions should fall under. For one group, it was a particularly difficult exercise, and it was stated that

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“the model didn’t really work for us... we were struggling to drop things into boxes”, Whilst two groups attempted to record their envisaged systems, this was done without assigning them to a specific leverage point with a fluid use of the designated columns. Results below:

Envisaged System	Transformative Interventions	How to prompt/ deepen/ enable...
<p>Projects funded to encourage children/ young people/ schools to explore, understand the issue and what the future may look like if we don’t intervene</p>	<p>Bring children and young people on board from an early age</p>	<p>Education on where food comes from and how it is cultivated/ grown/ transformed/ transported.</p> <p>Plant 2 Plate programme</p> <p>London Community Kitchen, Harrow & Brent</p>
<p>Government stopping energy drinks, inclusion of chemicals in food. Instead, Government making organic food more affordable, promoting sustainable/ safe food preservation (e.g. food drying) and enabling planning in urban areas to leave small scale local growing of food.</p> <p>Government to include health warnings on food packaging (similar to cigarette packaging) and to ban advertising of food and drink with negative health impacts on social media (e.g. Prime)</p> <p>Government banning or having more control of mass production of non-sustainable clothing (e.g. Shein)</p>		

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Envisaged System	Transformative Interventions	How to prompt/ deepen/ enable...
Proactive systems - instead of reactionary changes	Big industries	Shareholders, politicians, policymakers
Collective 'us' mindset	More autonomy for local communities to have agency in biodiversity issues. Perception changes on what someone's community is (religious/ local/ national/ global)	Volunteering Challenge individualist behaviour. Highlight the impact a single person or vote can make.
	School/ canteen meals from local sources	Local farm Sundays
Balanced native flora and fauna (ecosystem) Self-sustaining/ Sustainable/ Cyclical Sustainable sustenance - Raised awareness, consciousness	Education Knowledge share Legislation and Policy change (cross-party, a-political) Cross-departmental conversations in national and local government	Community projects/ interventions/ social media Schools teaching children and young people where food comes from Can we demonstrate how increased intervention in local community work results in a positive impact on NHS expenditure and crime rates? Curriculum change – what is the value? How can we demonstrate it? What is the cost of sick days to UK economy? Mental health champions? Or company gives an afternoon off for employee to take a walk-in nature Surveys/ feedback

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Envisaged System	Transformative Interventions	How to prompt/ deepen/ enable...
		Educate people to make better decisions around food/ consumption/ travel

The activity drew attention to the importance of engaging participants in a way that is meaningful, where they feel able to positively contribute without too much theory. One participant questioned the use of the framework:

I felt incredibly frustrated at the Leverage Points today, and perhaps this is a barrier to engaging black and brown people. It was wordy and confusing, and made everyone try to fit in within a white framework

The participant and her wider group felt the leverage point framework and the table they were asked to complete, “raised various questions” including requiring them to “fit ideas into a system” which made at least some members of the group “feel uncomfortable”. They “struggled to make sense of the framework” and identified the “leverage framework in itself as a barrier.” They questioned the role of academics in relation to the community in this process asking:

Do we as community members need to know about leverage systems? How much time should we devote to it? Or should the academics be sorting that out?

One frustrated participant followed-up on this dimension, by sending an email on her feedback to GL and GB. This group opted to use a blank piece of paper instead of the given framework. Below is a digital version of what they produced:

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Despite the challenges encountered engaging with the Leverage Point(s) activity, it led to a rich discussion and valuable insights were captured.

The main themes of the discussion were associated with a view that changing mindsets was important, *“How do we change the mindsets of people to make an impact?”* There was an acknowledgment that socio-economic factors present barriers to ethnic minority communities' engagement with nature and biodiversity (in the UK), but poor engagement and a lack of interest amongst more affluent ethnic minority communities was also identified as an issue:

I've heard Asians in the past, say to me, I'd rather play golf for four hours, then come to one of your walks and waste my time walking for four hours.

In terms of changing mindsets, it was discussed that getting people outdoors and into nature was a first good step.

First and foremost, let's get people into nature and be present there... and then once people are in and start enjoying being in, at one, being present, then you bring in these biodiversity agendas. How do we get the message out of health and wellbeing to Black, Asian, minority ethnic communities? Health and wellbeing is this westernised, commercialised concept – whether you look at yoga, whether it's stuff that's out in nature through a western lens.

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This led to consideration of circles of influences within communities, as it was felt that it is not enough to have a “token” person of colour on a programme which attracts a predominantly white audience (e.g. Anita Rani on Countryfile). There needs to be more grass-root community influencers and community forums to raise awareness in the South Asian and Black communities (as these would be more likely to be respected and connected with). One potential lever noted was whether sacred spaces could also be nature spaces through places of worship. Scriptures of multiple faiths (the Qur'an, the Book of Bhagavad Gita, the Guru Granth Sahibji were mentioned as holy books) are embedded with a lot of nature examples and stories, and using these, particularly through Sunday schools, could influence different thinking around biodiversity for children. Another group picked up this theme, desiring changes to the school curriculum, but also in relation to broader education.

Whether it's educating children at schools, whether it's educating communities, particularly ...BAME, whether it's educating government, but we also started talking about educating the biggest influencers. And ultimately, the biggest influencers are the big corporations... the food companies, the clothing manufacturers, etc. And then who influences them? Well ultimately its shareholders and who influences shareholders? Well ultimately, it's us, whether we see that directly or not, but it's us. And then we talked about education, sharing of knowledge. And I guess to a degree, Dadima's is doing that, but it's how we can expand that...

Educating the government, in relation to changing policy was recognised as a challenge, particularly as many local and national governments operate on four-year voting cycles, whereas biodiversity interventions may need to be twenty-, fifty- or one-hundred-year commitments. Lots of desires for changes to legislation were raised, some that wouldn't be affected by the lengthy time concern: including health warnings on foods, subsidising organic food, banning advertising of certain foods and drinks, restricting mass producing of certain products e.g. fast fashion linked to modern day slavery. Observing that policymakers are often swayed by popular opinion, was an incentive to bring a collective message. Local authority workers within the Learning Community encouraged members of the group to engage with consultations about these issues to make sure that their voices are heard and inform policy. Framing things became important here: that nature improves wellbeing, and prescribing a walk in nature is more cost effective for the NHS and beneficial to the person than half an hour learning about CBT (Cognitive Behavioural Therapy) with a medical practitioner. Some are hopeful in collectively raising a voice, pointing to the Me-Too movement beginning as a grassroots initiative but garnering support. There were concerns raised, however, when thinking about the national biodiversity agenda, in relation to climate anxiety:

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the way I manage my anxiety around this agenda is through local and community, because as soon as I start thinking national and global, the anxiety gets worse. So, I think about it by what difference am I making to this agenda within the communities I work with? - the people I talk to

Interventions at community level were identified as a lever for all groups, and even to influence the policymakers: “essentially influencing policymakers and government through doing so much at grassroots level that they have no choice ultimately but to listen to what's being said.” There were great examples shared of different groups within villages, committed to their areas of biodiversity, and working together, and how it would be good to replicate this all over the country. It was noted, however, that there was not a lot of volunteering for biodiversity related work observed within the BAME communities.

If we talked to the Aston Road nature reserve, if we talk to Natural England, they've got 1000s of volunteers. But it'd be interesting to know how many of those volunteers are [from] BAME [backgrounds], and I suspect there aren't that many. And we need to understand why that is and how we can get more BAME [communities] volunteering.

This led to identifying who is one's community:

Why is someone from the BAME community or Indian community in particular, volunteering at a temple rather than volunteering somewhere else? What does that person perceive their community to be? Do they perceive their community to be only their religious community? Or is it as a nation or global, and it's changing people's perceptions of thinking of their community as being a bit wider scale than just what is within their own sort of demographic.

The community level was identified as the best place to focus attention, once we determined who is our community, recognising that “we can all do something right now – and we're probably already doing it”, with friends, family, children and grandchildren.

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Participatory filmmaking

GB and BC (filmmaker) shared information about what Participatory filmmaking is and can be. There were some examples shared and a handout with practical filmmaking tips (see below):

ASK YOURSELF → **How do i want my audience to feel?** → **How do i best make them feel this?**

Composition, light, sound & location all affect how we feel and will add and expand your story and the message you want to communicate

WHERE IS THE CAMERA?
Here are some options

- Far away?
- Close up?
- Looking down?
- Looking up?

Each one of these make the viewer feel something different. Ask yourself how they make you feel and is this the correct feeling to help tell your story.

WHERE IS THE SUBJECT?
Here are some options

- Sat down?
- Stood up?
- Off to the side and facing into the space?
- Off to the side and facing away from the space?

Again each one of these make the viewer feel something different. Ask yourself how they make you feel and is this the correct feeling to help tell your story.

WHERE IS THE SUBJECT LOOKING?

- At the lens? (therefore the viewer)
- Off the side and into the space?
- Off the side and away from the space?

The closer the subject looks toward the lens the more personal it feels. (as if the subject is addressing the viewer)

The further the subject looks away the less personal it feels. (the viewer feels like an observer)

LIGHT

2 simple things to think about -

- 1) Is my subject visible? Not to light and not to dark.
- 2) How does the lighting on my subject make me feel and why?

3 simple ways to change light

- 1) Move the subject.
- 2) Wait until there is better light. (morning and evening are better times for natural light)
- 3) Use lamps and move them around.

Tips

- Lighting from the side looks better than from in-front or behind.
- Look at your subject through camera. The camera sees light different to us.

SOUND

Above all we need the viewer to hear our subject or the narration clearly

If you're outside - Stay out of the wind! If needed move your subject to a sheltered spot. If you can't put your body in-between the wind and the microphone.

If you're inside - Rooms with bare walls or floors cause more echo. Echo rarely makes things sound good. Rooms with soft things like carpets, curtains etc are better.

Tips

- Listen back! Record a short section on your phone & listen back to how it sounds
- Use the audio recorder on a second phone & place it near your subject for better sound

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Time pressures and outside noise and weather prevented experimenting with participatory film at this workshop, but there will be a further optional online session with BC (the filmmaker) for extra tips and an opportunity to ask questions, as well as dedicated time built into future workshops. Participants were encouraged to keep posting their images and short videos within the Learning Community WhatsApp group but to keep the “uncompressed” originals on their phones for a future film.

Wrap up and next steps

Eight of the eleven participants selected for the Learning Community attended Workshop 2. GL contacted those four unable to be at Workshop 1 to bring them up to speed. The three people that haven't been able to attend either of the first two workshops are included in the Learning Community WhatsApp group and some are posting.

GB has completed 30-minute interviews online with all participants who attended Workshop 1. She will interview the two additional members of the Learning Community who came to Workshop 2 the first week in May.

The Learning Community WhatsApp group with all participants and researchers is being well used – typically multiple posts daily. The posts and interactions include photographs, stories, musings, book recommendations, and relevant articles and have enabled species identification.

There was not time to complete thoughts on postcards as planned, but there were other opportunities for reflection throughout the session.

The Community left reflecting on what Citizen science project they may like to engage with, and considering how they might project material for a participatory film.

ⁱ Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic communities or 'BAME' is frequently used to group all ethnic minorities. The term can disguise differences in outcomes between ethnic groups. Many ethnic minorities themselves say they do not like the term 'BAME', a finding reinforced by recent research commissioned by the [Cabinet Office Race Disparity Unit \(RDU\)](#)